

This dataset was prepared for the participants in the second championship phase of the Open challenge organized by the CHAIMELEON project for the training of AI models to resolve a specific clinical question related to Breast cancer:

predict histology subtype (Ductal Carcinoma In Situ - DCIS, Invasive Ductal Carcinoma - IDC, Invasive Lobular Carcinoma - ILC, or Other).

All 631 breast cases (images and clinical data) collected until November 2023 were initially taken. Then 22 cases were excluded due to missing diagnosis MG study and 21 due to unknown histology type.

From the 588 resulting cases, 411 were selected for the training partition and so included in this dataset:

41 with DCIS, 302 with IDC, 46 with ILC and 22 with Other histology subtype

Only studies of Mammographies were selected.

All the original series (DICOM) are included.

Only images from diagnosis.

In the Open Challenge only demographic and diagnosis information (excl. biopsy-related information) was shared with the participants, but here the complete clinical data is included in the eforms.json file.

The ground truth for the clinical question in that case is in the variable:

biopsy_tumor_histotype

ID: b66781db-8b21-4a30-ac0d-8eaa2a4c0ecc

URL: <https://chaimoleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/b66781db-8b21-4a30-ac0d-8eaa2a4c0ecc/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chaimoleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 411

Subjects count: 411

Age range: Between 27 years and 97 years

Sex: Female

Body part(s): BREAST

Modality: MG, Unknown